

Improving archaeological models for horse use at Botai: a response to Outram et al.

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In their reply, Outram and colleagues¹ articulate three key criticisms pertaining to bit wear, biomolecules, and archaeological context, which we will address in sequence. Before beginning, we remind the reader of the criteria outlined by Outram et al.² to identify bit use: A) dentine exposure, B) diastema bone formation, and C) enamel exposure in excess of 5mm, with parallel sides, lacking severe buccal or lingual enamel exposure. To the first point, we establish that dentine exposure in the form of circular/oval pits cannot be considered reliable evidence of bit damage, showing that such features can be produced by natural processes (e.g., enamel hypoplasia) and differ drastically from dentine exposure caused by bit use.³ Recognizing the very different mechanisms involved in the formation of hypoplastic lesions and cementum bands,³ it is unsurprising – indeed, expected – that such hypoplastic lesions are not tightly correlated with cementum banding. Next, Outram et al. appear to concede that comparable diastema bone formation is also found in Pleistocene wild horses, and therefore cannot uniquely distinguish ridden horses. The case for Botai transport thus now rests solely on the third criterion, the shape of exposed enamel.

Outram and colleagues go to great lengths to highlight uneven buccal and lingual wear on one wild horse tooth from Bluefish Caves – a tooth selected to demonstrate anterior pit-form hypoplasia. They are quite mistaken, however, in extrapolating confidence for the Botai tooth from this observation. Many wild horses in our dataset also exhibit enamel exposures of greater than 5mm – roughly parallel in shape, and with minute or absent buccal/lingual enamel exposure (Figure 1). These demonstrate, as with dentine exposure and diastema bone formation, that without a careful consideration of natural defects, parallel enamel exposures are no “smoking gun” for bit use. A new photo of the Botai tooth (Fig. 1B)¹ reiterates the absence of parallel morphology, showing two enamel exposure zones nearly bisected by a cementum ridge, corresponding to the peak of cementum thickness on the lingual margin. Curiously, areas of potential buccal and lingual enamel exposure in this photo are still obscured by excavation dirt patina, making them impossible to assess (Fig. 1B).¹

In wild horses, the anterior margin of the second premolar is a natural focal point for dietary wear, and the morphology of enamel exposure appears to be influenced by a number of factors, including 1) the amount and distribution of cementum around the occlusal/coronal area of the tooth crown, 2) degree of abrasiveness of the diet, and 3) morphology of the anterior cusp of the tooth. Teeth such as the Botai specimen that terminate in a sharper cusp are far more likely to produce approximately parallel-shaped exposures than those with a rounded cusp, like those shown in Outram et al.’s Fig. 1C and 1D. Consequently, it is particularly important to carefully consider developmental defects on such specimens. Given the obvious sources of potential confounding error on the Botai tooth (indication of hypoplasia and reduced cementum deposition), we encourage our colleagues to directly test dentine exposures through histological thin-sections, as outlined in our Figure 4,³ and to investigate other skeletal and pathological features that should be present in the assemblage, if the horses were used for transport,⁴⁻⁹ rather than to base the entire hypothesis for Botai horse transport on one area of exposed enamel from a single tooth.

In the second substantive portion of their critique, Outram and colleagues defend their inferences derived from stable isotopes, asserting that their comparative datasets rule out any possibility that seasonal hunting of wild horses could have produced the observed patterning in deuterium isotopes. In order for this to be true, the reader must first be supremely confident that this small set of modern comparative data, derived from only domestic animals and what is now known to be a different taxon (*E. caballus*), have fully characterized the range of relevant sources of deuterium variability that could have contributed to Botai ceramics. We note that Outram et al.'s own analysis shows this not to be the case – all five of the samples identified as 'milk' at Botai actually fall far outside the variability of their reference horse milk dataset (Fig. 3D).² Given the exceedingly indirect relationship between the deuterium proxy and the actual phenomenon of interest (milk production/consumption), it is imperative to test for more direct indicators of equine dairying, such as dietary proteins from human dental calculus, which have been successfully detected in other early Eurasian pastoral contexts¹⁰ but have so far failed to emerge at Botai.¹¹ We note that after calibration and correction, the earliest such proteins (referenced in this discussion,¹ from the Black Sea region) are dated to an exceedingly wide range of ca. 3300-2200 cal. BCE, most of which falls far outside the chronological window of the Botai culture.¹¹

Finally, the authors revisit a handful of archaeological phenomena, where once again misplaced confidence in indirect proxies has led them astray. High levels of soil phosphorus can be influenced by domestic animal penning, but are also generated by unrelated processes such as human waste and refuse,¹² and the isolated structures identified so far at Botai sites would likely accommodate only a very small number of animals.¹³ We urge our colleagues to bolster their argument using more direct proxies, such as fecal biomarkers and sedimentary DNA, and to test these hypothesized "corrals" against control zones, modern corrals, and hunter-gatherer sites/features. While the leopard spotting found in Botai *E. przewalskii*¹⁴ is indeed interesting, it is also commensurate with patterns found in Paleolithic wild horses.¹⁵ As to whether the lack of a "schlepp effect" distinguishes a wild from a domestic assemblage, we note that it is quite common for Paleolithic mass harvesting of horses to produce assemblages with a large number of whole carcasses.¹⁶ A single cranial fracture taken as evidence of "pole-axing" – a partial, depressed fracture on the upper maxilla of one horse¹⁷ – is quite unlike any features seen in early domestic horse assemblages chosen for intentional slaughter, wherein animals are typically struck efficiently in the frontal or parietal bones (Figure 2A).^{18,19} Finally, in response to Outram et al.'s claim of no evidence for a hunting toolkit, here we reprint images of used hunting implements found in association with horse remains from Botai, along with impact fractures from the ribs showing that animals were killed via projectile (Figure 2B).

Outram and colleagues close with a rhetorical question – how can we explain the settlement of Botai people in sedentary villages, and near-exclusive dietary focus on horses, without invoking domestication? While we cannot, of course, provide a comprehensive alternative model via this simple critique, we note that the transition to specialized domestic horse herding has almost universally stimulated rapid and drastic *increases* in human mobility, in part due to the unique ecological requirements of horses. In contrast, many Holocene hunter-gatherers made sustained use of areas with predictable resources. As early as the early Upper Paleolithic, horse mass harvesting sites have been at least sometimes accompanied by habitation structures, burials, and other permanent structures.¹⁶ Though we agree that the apparent local specialization in horse hunting at Botai would be notable amid the broader Holocene decline of wild horse populations, we encourage our colleagues to embrace sustained scientific inquiry using emerging technologies and improved proxies – wherever the search may lead us.

Figure 1. Anterior and lateral views of lower second premolars from Natural Trap Cave (KU 41708, 43179, and 41957) showing parallel-sided, anterior enamel exposure far in excess of 5 mm in height, despite the lack of appreciable buccal or lingual wear. Note that KU 41708 and 41957 were evaluated in our original study, but because of their thick cementum covering were excluded from further analysis pertaining to hypoplasia.

Figure 2. Bone/antler projectiles found in excavations at Botai (1), showing impact damage, along with horse rib bones showing evidence of impact during hunting (2), modified from Olsen.²⁰ Botai horse skull with depressed maxilla fracture (3), as compared to area of typical lesions from slaughter of domestic horses from “pole-axing” in archaeological assemblages (modified from Olsen¹⁴), and Pazyryk horse showing true “pole-axing” marks, a sharp traumatic perforation of the braincase (4).

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